

Alpine dragon- and damselfly communities of anthropogenic habitats. An interplay between habitat requirements and temperature.

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Introduction

Alpine environments harbor a large diversity of natural habitats and thus are hotspots of global biological diversity (STEINBAUER et al. 2016; ANTONELLI et al. 2018; PINKERT et al. 2024). Concerningly, while natural habitats are on the decline worldwide (SALA et al. 2000) human habitat modification has extended up to alpine elevations spurred on by demands of tourism, energy production and recently conservation (FAIT et al. 2020; BROSE et al. 2022; GERFAND et al. 2024). Peatlands and freshwater habitats harbor a large part of the Alpine threatened biodiversity, but remain underrepresented in conservation efforts (BRAGAZZA 2009). Artificial ponds have been proposed as stepping-stone or substitute habitats, that could boost population sizes of alpine freshwater species and assist them in shifting their ranges and better track climate change (ILG & OERTLI 2014; OERTLI et al. 2014; FAIT et al. 2020; GERFAND et al. 2024) and hundreds of pond creation and restoration projects have been carried out across several countries to establish habitats for biodiversity, with costs amounting to millions of Euros (BARTRONS et al. 2024). However, little is known about the interactive effect of temperature and anthropogenic disturbance on invertebrate communities, with alpine species often being particularly vulnerable to human impacts (NEGRO et al. 2010; KAŠÁK et al. 2013; ASSANDRI & BAZZI 2022). Thus, the conservation value of alpine artificial water bodies remains therefore unclear.

Methods

Focusing on dragonflies and damselflies, whose semi-aquatic life cycle and ectothermic nature make them particularly sensitive to temperature (HASSALL 2015) and habitat conditions (BÍLKOVÁ et al. 2025), we examined the taxonomic and functional composition on 28 natural and 13 anthropogenically altered sites spanning a 2000-meter elevational gradient in the European Alps. This altitudinal gradient comprises a wide heterogeneity of habitats (ASSANDRI 2019), which range from natural alpine wetlands harbouring boreo-alpine specialists like *Aeshna subarctica* and *A. caerulea* (ASSANDRI et al. 2022) to large and warm lakes, harbouring thermophilous species like *Trithemis annulata* (PUFF et al. 2023). Our aim was to assess how diversity, abundance and functional traits change along elevation and if natural and anthropogenic habitats follow similar trends.

Keywords: Alpine environments, artificial habitats, Bergman's rule, freshwater biodiversity, elevational gradient, habitat filtering.

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Results & Discussion

Our results demonstrate that, similar to continental scales (PINKERT et al. 2017; ZEUSS et al. 2017; ACQUAH-LAMPTEY et al. 2020; MÄHN et al. 2023), dragonflies follow trends in morphology and life history at a regional scale, along an elevational gradient, as expected by Bergmann's rule (SHELOMI 2012) and thermal melanism hypothesis (CLUSELLA TRULLAS et al. 2007). In damselflies however, functional responses to temperature, especially morphology, are different and their abundances strongly declined below moderate temperatures, while those of dragonflies were unaffected by temperature (Figure 1). This suggests that dragonflies are better adapted to the cold temperatures of higher elevations, while damselflies seem far less able to adapt their morphology to cold environments. Additionally, both dragon- and damselfly communities at anthropogenic alpine sites were composed of more thermophile species than at natural alpine sites, indicating poor support of the natural and unique faunal elements via artificial water bodies (Figure 1). This must be considered for conservation aimed at maintaining and improving the status of alpine specialists (ILG & OERTLI 2014; OERTLI et al. 2014), which not only constitute certain odonate lineages but also distinct parts of the functional diversity, as we show. The ecological dynamics of alpine artificial water bodies stem from the additive constrains of temperature and anthropogenic disturbance. This dual constraint appears to hinder typical alpine species from colonising these man-made environments, posing a challenge for their role in biodiversity conservation amid global warming and biodiversity decline. See PUFF et al. (2025) for more details.

Figure 1: NMDS ordination of species communities. Panel (a) shows site scores with arrows indicating site variable loadings; panel (b) shows scaled species scores with trait loadings. The ratio of anthropogenic to natural sites was calculated from study data. Alpine species are defined as those with a Temperature Index < 6 (TERMAAT et al. 2019). Genus names in (b) are abbreviated to the first three letters. Modified from PUFF et al. (2025).

References

- ACQUAH-LAMPTEY D., BRÄNDLE M., BRANDL R. & PINKERT S., 2020: Temperature-driven color lightness and body size variation scale to local assemblages of European Odonata but are modified by propensity for dispersal. *Ecol. Evol.*, 10(16): 8936–8948. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.6596>
- ANTONELLI A., KISSLING W. D., FLANTUA S. G. A., BERMÚDEZ M. A., MULCH A., MUELLNER-RIEHL A. N., KREFT H., LINDER H. P., BADGLEY C., FJELDSÅ J., FRITZ S. A., RAHBEK C., HERMAN F., HOOGHIEMSTRA H. & HOORN C., 2018: Geological and climatic influences on mountain biodiversity. *Nat. Geosci.*, 11(10): 718–725. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-018-0236-z>
- ASSANDRI G., 2019: A critical review of the odonate fauna of Trentino: Annotated check-list and new relevant data for Italy (Insecta: Odonata). *Fragmenta Entomologica*, 51(1): 75–88. <https://doi.org/10.4081/fe.2019.339>
- ASSANDRI G. & BAZZI G., 2022: Natural and anthropogenic determinants of peatland dragonfly assemblages: Implications for management and conservation. *Biodivers. Conserv.*, 31(2): 703–722. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-022-02358-0>
- ASSANDRI G. & BAZZI G., 2022: Natural and anthropogenic determinants of peatland dragonfly assemblages: Implications for management and conservation. *Biodivers. Conserv.*, 31(2): 703–722. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-022-02358-0>
- BARTRONS M., TROCHINE C., Blicharska M., OERTLI B., LAGO M. & BRUCET, S., 2024: Unlocking the potential of ponds and pondscapes as nature-based solutions for climate resilience and beyond: Hundred evidences. *J. Environ. Manag.*, 359, 120992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120992>
- BÍLKOVÁ E., ŠIGUTOVÁ H., PYSZKO P., PRIELOŽNÁ V. & DOLNÝ A., 2025: Adapting a country-specific Dragonfly Biotic Index: Framework for seven Central European countries and transboundary pattern analysis. *Ecol. Indic.*, 170: 113111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113111>
- BRAGAZZA L., 2009: Conservation priority of Italian Alpine habitats: A floristic approach based on potential distribution of vascular plant species. *Biodivers. Conserv.*, 18(11): 2823–2835. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-009-9609-3>
- BROSSE M., BENATEAU S., GAUDARD A., STAMM C. & ALTERMATT, F., 2022: The importance of indirect effects of climate change adaptations on alpine and pre-alpine freshwater systems. *Ecol. Solut. Evid.*, 3(1): e12127. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12127>
- CLUSELLA TRULLAS S., VAN WYK J. H. & SPOTILA J. R., 2007: Thermal melanism in ectotherms. *J. Therm. Biol.*, 32(5): 235–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtherbio.2007.01.013>
- FAIT P., DEMIERRE E., ILG C. & OERTLI B., 2020: Small mountain reservoirs in the Alps: New habitats for alpine freshwater biodiversity? *Aquat. Conserv. Mar. Freshw. Ecosyst.*, 30(4): 617–630. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3306>
- GERFAND B., ARTHAUD F., EVETTE A., TESTI B., PEYRAS L. & GAUCHERAND S., 2024: Ecological quality of snowmaking reservoirs in the Alps and management perspectives. *Aquat. Sci.*, 87(1): 9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-024-01136-0>
- HASSALL C., 2015: Odonata as candidate macroecological barometers for global climate change. *Freshw. Sci.*, 34(3): 1040–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1086/682210>
- ILG C. & OERTLI B., 2014: How can we conserve cold stenotherm communities in warming Alpine ponds? *Hydrobiologia*, 723(1): 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-013-1538-1>
- KAŠÁK J., MAZALOVÁ M., ŠIPOŠ J. & KURAS T., 2013: The effect of alpine ski-slopes on epigeic beetles: Does even a nature-friendly management make a change? *J. Insect Conserv.*, 17(5): 975–988. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-013-9579-3>
- MAHN L. A., HOF C., BRANDL R. & PINKERT S., 2023: Beyond latitude: Temperature, productivity and thermal niche conservatism drive global body size variation in Odonata. *Global Ecol. Biogeogr.*, 32(5): 656–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13661>
- NEGRO M., ISAIA M., PALESTRINI C., SCHOENHOFER A. & ROLANDO A., 2010: The impact of high-altitude ski pistes on ground-dwelling arthropods in the Alps. *Biodivers. Conserv.*, 19(7): 1853–1870. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-010-9808-y>
- OERTLI B., ILG C., ANGÉLIBERT S., BOLLIGER J., GROVADORE J., DEMIERRE E., JULLIAND C., FINGER-STICH A., FORRÉ C., FROSSARD P.-A., LEFORT F., MAYENCOURT M., PIANTINI U. & SCHMID S., 2014: Freshwater biodiversity under warming pressure in the Alps: A methodological framework for prioritization of restoration areas for small waterbodies. *J. Prot. Mount. Areas Res. Manag.*, 6/1: 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.1553/ecomont-6-1s23>
- PINKERT S., BRANDL R. & ZEUSS D., 2017: Colour lightness of dragonfly assemblages across North America and Europe. *Ecography*, 40(9): 1110–1117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.02578>
- PINKERT S., FARWIG N., KAWAHARA A. & JETZ W., 2024: Global hotspots of butterfly diversity in a warming world. In *Review at Nature Portfolio*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4437399/v1>
- PUFF F., HILPOLD A., SCHULZE C. H. & GUARIENTO E., 2023: *Trithemis annulata* (Insecta, Libellulidae) reaches the northernmost Italian region Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol. *Gredleriana*, 23: 107–114.
- PUFF F., SCHULZE C. H., NOVELLA-FERNANDEZ R., HILPOLD A., PINKERT S. & GUARIENTO E., 2025: Artificial ponds do not support the natural functional and taxonomic composition of alpine dragon- and damselfly communities. *Global Ecology and Conservation*: e03708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2025.e03708>
- SALA O. E., STUART CHAPIN F., III, ARMESTO J. J., BERLOW E., BLOOMFIELD J., DIRZO R., HUBER-SANWALD E., HUENNEKE L. F., JACKSON R. B., KINZIG A., LEEMANS R., LODGE D. M., MOONEY H. A., OESTERHELD M., POFF N. L., SYKES M. T., WALKER B. H., WALKER M. & WALL D. H., 2000: Global Biodiversity Scenarios for the Year 2100. *Sci.*, 287(5459): 1770–1774. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.287.5459.1770>
- SHELOMI M., 2012: Where Are We Now? Bergmann's Rule Sensu Lato in Insects. *Am. Nat.*, 180(4): 511–519. <https://doi.org/10.1086/667595>
- ZEUSS D., BRUNZEL S. & BRANDL R., 2017: Environmental drivers of voltinism and body size in insect assemblages across Europe. *Global Ecol. Biogeogr.*, 26(2): 154–165. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12525>